

INSTRUCTIONAL DELIVERY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The main concern of the study was to assess the instructional delivery of the Senior High School teachers of the Oblates of Saint Joseph Schools with the end goal of proposing an instructional approaches program. Specifically, this study assessed the instructional delivery of teachers, the extent of technical assistance provided, and the problems encountered in instructional delivery. A descriptive correlational method was used to identify the relationship between technical assistance received and the instructional delivery of teachers. Results revealed that the teachers' ability to deliver their instruction effectively was influenced by the level of technical assistance received by the respondents. Teachers' practices are expected to be competent for effective instructional delivery as manifested in terms of content, approaches, assessment, and course management. From among the technical assistance provided, recipient knowledge increase received the highest assessment from the respondents. With respect to problems encountered, class size, absenteeism and students' inability to think critically obtained the highest assessment from the teachers. An instructional approaches program which includes foundations for instructional practice, framework, and guidelines for teachers and staff development program was the output of the study. Furthermore, teachers' practices on the content, approaches, assessment and course management are highly manifested based on the results. From among the technical assistance provided namely information transfer and referral, building capacity, behavior and system change, shared learning and recipient knowledge increase, the latter was found to be the one the teachers experienced the most. The teachers' ability to deliver his or her instruction effectively is influenced by the level of technical assistance he or she receives. Though problems concerning instructional delivery such as class size, absenteeism, and students' inability to think critically, the respondents do not seem to consider these as problems as they are outside of teachers' control. However, concerns on skills, strategies, knowledge upgrade, dealing with students, and managing differences were concerns that were also encountered by the teachers but have been identified to be within their control. An instructional approaches program which includes foundations for instructional practice, framework, and guidelines for teachers and staff development program as an outcome of this study would be beneficial for both the teachers and the administrators alike. A proposed instructional approaches program was devised to address the weak areas of study and to be used as a guide for the school heads to supervise the instructional delivery of teachers in Senior High School.

Keywords: instructional delivery, practices, proposed instructional approaches program, technical assistance